

STUDENTS CHALLENGES IN LEARNING SPEAKING SKILLS

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ABSTRACT

Students who have speaking skills can handle with university tasks and it can serve as a window to other parts of the world. When students acquire speaking skills they can have conversation with foreign people, can participate in online conversations or develop their other skills by its help. The article below provides data about problems that usually learners face while learning speaking.

INTRODUCTION

EFL students face many difficulties within the classroom during their learning process among them. While learning speaking students may face a range of challenges and in fact they are considered to be a part of learning process. Some students overcome or solve the challenges with less difficulty while some other part of students, actually big number of students, find it difficult to solve or overcome without help from outside. However, the help by teacher and peers makes the work done easier which is witnessed in majority of the cases. For example, those who are learning speaking in a group with peers usually find it easier due the support that comes from surrounding.

The problems they have distinctive features. They may be related to one of the followings: linguistic knowledge they have, dare, ability, psychology, society around them (yes even society!) and culture. So here we enlisted and identified the issues those are common for learners:

Linguistic Problems:

Fluency

It's the ability to produce speech without hesitation. According to Hedge (2000:261) who claims that:

- Fluency means responding coherently with the turns of the conversation, linking words and phrases using intelligible pronunciation and appropriate intonation, and doing all this without undue hesitation.

Through here, we can notice that the most difficult challenge in learning English is speaking fluently following certain features which give the students' speech a sign of being normal and natural with clear logical

connection of ideas. Moreover, the proficiency to use the items of the conversation coherently without hesitation, and this is the challenge that most of our students cannot rich it. According to Trunbury (1999:93) “fluency is a skill, it is the ability to process the language speedily and easily”. In fact most of students misrepresent and confuse their ideas when they attempt to perform their own practice.

Accuracy

Accuracy is the ability to produce grammatically correct sentences and it focuses on the correct use of grammar and vocabulary and other skills. To achieve accuracy the learner need to devote some attention to the form i.e. “getting it right”. It is often difficult for the learners to focus on the form and meaning at the same time. Accuracy requires attention and this latter need to time. Researchers suggest that learners are more accurate the more time they have available (ibid: 93).Among other difficulties have a relation with pronunciation; the words that are difficult to pronounce are more difficult to learn. Potentially; difficult words will be those that contain sounds which are unfamiliar to some groups of learners. (Trunbury, 2002: 27).so intelligible comprehensible pronunciation of speech is important and it’s considered as a key to avoid pronunciation errors which frustrate successful communication.

Grammar and vocabulary

Students lack of useful and appropriate expression and catch the right one to express an opinion or different sorts of things. Students errors can be categorized in two forms: - Form related error: it includes miss election, malformations, and spelling and pronunciation errors. - Meaning related errors: it occurs when words that have similar or related meaning are confused and the wrong choice is made. Generally, most of our students go on making the same errors even when such errors are obvious.

Psychological Problems

In fact these problems are originated from the great diversity of the learners within the same class and inhibition is one of many psychological problems. The problem of inhibition is related to the students themselves because of shyness and fear of making mistakes, this latter will lead to the criticism of their peers, as well as; their teachers and they think that whenever they make mistakes/errors are in their views signs of ignorance. This proves by Ur (ibid: 121) who claims that:

Learners are often inhibited about trying to say things in foreign language in the classroom worried about making mistakes, fearful of criticism, or losing face or simply shy of attention that their speech attracts.

We can claim that inhibition is a bridge to the psychology of the students to be shy, fearful, and feel embarrassment when they try to speak in the classroom.

The Social Problems

No one can deny that students who share the same native language have different perspective and styles.

The use of L1: the use of L1 is a problem because many students keep or prefer to use their native language (mother tongue) rather than English to perform such tasks in their classrooms. This habit happens when one of the students is explaining something important to his classmate using L1 to express. According to UR , mother tongue use in classes where all or a number of learners share the same mother tongue they tend to use it because it’s easier, it feels unnatural to speak to one another in foreign language and because they feel less exposed

if they are speaking their mother tongue (1998:121).

The social environment has a great impact on the learning process, as well as, the use of the language to express their ideas; many students go back to their mother tongue to speak because they have a deep knowledge of their language.

Cultural Problems

Speaking over laps with other areas which control and determine our structure of the conversation, According to Harmer (2001) speakers from the same cultural back ground know how to speak with each other, and kind of language they can use. Such cultural habits that shared by all people determine behaviors in such conversation situation. It also determine how women and men speak to each other, how conversation is framed when the participants are of different social or professional status. This leads to guide our behavior in number of well recognized speech. Socio-cultural rules and habits change overtime but at any a given moment they exist in the public conscious (247). Through here, we can say that the cultural back ground determines the perspective, personalities, and the conversation style, and attitudes; this leads to find out differences types of students. Examples for these are talkative one, silent and other ones who feel shy to speak in front of their classmates.

To sum up, there are different types of issues that can be found among students who are learning speaking and all of them are distinctive, differ from each other. To overcome these issues demand time and hard work from teacher, learner and even peers of students. If this "team" works together well gradually the issues will disappear.

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